

D5.2

Leadership and Decision-Making Diagnosis Report

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-Roles tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
Task 5.3	Design of Action Plan based on findings of D5.2

GEARING-ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectoral collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HR	Human Resources
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SD	Standard Deviation
WFC	Work-Family Conflict
WLB	Work-Life Balance
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

This document is the *Leadership and Decision-Making Diagnosis Report (D5.2)* by WP5 leader University of Deusto.

The general objectives of the WP are focused on two main axes: (i) encourage equal participation of women and men in leadership and decision-making structures, and (ii) support awareness rising through the development of behavioral changes to promote inclusive leadership.

In order to achieve these aims, an Action Plan is being developed, and collated under Deliverables 5.3 (complete Action Plan and recommendations for GEPs) and 5.4 (specific design of training initiatives). One of the most relevant aspects in order to develop a good Action Plan is to build it on the grounds of a good diagnosis of the initial situation. And that is the purpose of this deliverable: to present and analyse the most relevant information available regarding leadership and decision-making processes in our GEP implementing partners, identifying main points based on which interventions can be made.

In order to be able to identify the most relevant information, qualitative and quantitative techniques have been used. From a quantitative point of view, the process consisted of gathering all the indicators related to leadership and decision-making processes present in the Institutional Baseline Assessments (mainly linked to the shares of women and men in management teams).

From a qualitative perspective, analysis with people in top management positions in all GEPs have been conducted. Then, each GEPI analysed its own interviews and identified the most relevant topics, under a common methodological framework developed by the UDEUSTO research team. UDEUSTO performed 16 interviews with all the members of the Board of Directors plus HR Manager and Financial Director. Besides, five focus groups were delivered: one with students, two with Teaching and Research Staff and two with Administrative Staff. In total, 29 women and 25 men took part in the process.

OBU carried out 12 interviews, 11 of which were face-to-face and one by phone, with participants from all four faculties involved (i.e. Oxford Brookes Business School, Health and Life Sciences, Technology Design and Environment and Humanities and Social Sciences). In addition, participants from Human Resources, Student Support Services and Marketing and Communications were interviewed. Four were men, and there were eight women. Finally, four were in an academic role with one at professorial level. Six were in leadership roles, three of whom were at the level of pro-vice chancellor.

ETAg conducted seven semi-structured interviews all heads of departments with the exception for the head of the Department of Analysis, as she is tightly connected to the GEARING-Roles project herself. Five of the interviewees were women and two were men. The interviews lasted

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for an average of 25 minutes. In addition to the face-to-face interviews, a representative of the evaluation committee and the Head of Communication were questioned by e-mail and asked to provide some additional insight into the topic regarding their specific area of expertise.

In the case of IGOT, the gathering of qualitative data involved 11 semi-structured interviews conducted to people in leadership positions (Dean of IGOT and the President of the IGOT's research unit - CEG), staff members (coordinator of undergraduate and master, among others) and PhD students. In addition, two workshops were also organised, one with members of the task force (IGOT's Dean, CEG's Director, IGOT's Executive Director, staff members, PhD students and administrative staff) and another with students ranging from graduation to PhD level. In total, 23 women and 16 men were involved.

At Sabanci University, qualitative data collection was conducted on two levels using two different qualitative research methods. We held six focus groups discussions with employees (academic and administrative) and students, involving a total of 28 participants and paying attention to the diversity of the sample; and conducted nine semi-structured in-depth interviews with people in administrative and academic decision-making positions, including those in highest management (President and two Vice-Presidents), a Dean, two Academic Directors, an Administrative Director as well as the former Director of HR and the former General Secretary

Finally, in the case of Faculty of Arts of UL, qualitative analysis is based on four interviews (with the Dean, Vice-Dean for Research, Vice-Dean for Quality and Research and with Students' Career Advisor), and four focus groups (with student representatives, academic staff, department heads and support services).

UDEUSTO collated all the reports and extracted common aspects, which can be addressed as a consortium, and issues specific to any of the organisations, for which some recommendation to include on their GEPs have been made. Furthermore, information about possible biases at the decision-making processes was gathered by means of a Workshop carried out by WP5 coordinators in the context of the Institutional Pairing visits (see Deliverable 5.4 and 5.5).

Once a general overview of the current situation of the organisations has been obtained, a questionnaire was administered to all the personnel of the six GEP implementing partners, in order to collect their view about different areas of leadership and decision-making. This questionnaire, which will be described with more detail section 3 of this report, has been developed by WP5 coordinators with inputs of all the partners, and administered through an online platform in four different languages (English, Spanish, Slovenian and Basque). It was then analysed using the SPSS software.

The present document is divided into two main sections. In the first one, the main issues arising from the leadership sections of the Institutional Assessment Reports and the qualitative analysis

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of the interviews are presented. Then, in the second section, the perceptions of the employees are presented through the analysis of the abovementioned questionnaire. The report closes with some final reflections and conclusions.

2. Qualitative Institutional Diagnosis

This section contains a summary of the different issues identified at each GEP implementing institution on their Institutional Assessment Reports, based on the interviews described above. The information provided aims to serve as a complement of the more quantitative diagnosis approach in the next section, and shows that most of the institutions have common challenges in leadership, with small variations due to several factors, such as the national context and the performance of the institution regarding gender equality.

2.1. IGOT

First, it is important to highlight how statistics on IGOT's Assessment Report show that there are gender imbalances in representation at Faculty level: The three main bodies at IGOT (management council, scientific council and pedagogic council) are men-dominated, with a very low participation rate for women.

From the qualitative information it can be concluded that, although participants showed different degrees of perception regarding gender inequalities underpinning the academic life of IGOT, both interviews presented a common storyline: an initial position of denial of an existing gender issue followed by a change of opinion after confrontation with extensive data from the gender audit. Recognition of existing inequalities is fundamental, and the availability of data, on the national and institutional level, had a great impact in prompting participants to provide explanations for those discrepancies.

With regards to gender inequalities in terms of access to leadership positions and decision-making bodies, the interviewees state that there is an institutional culture where competence is valued above all else. In any case, IGOT is a small school of the University of Lisbon and a number of its decision-making bodies require members to be full professors (or equivalent) in order to participate. As there are not many full professors, and even fewer women who are full professors, there is not much room for manoeuvre.

By referring to structural resistances and obstacles to a more inclusive gender policy at IGOT, the contradictions of 'politically correctness' (being in favour of gender equality in theory but not in practice) are highlighted. On a different note, the imbalance between women and men at IGOT are seen as a reflection of wider social inequalities. The self-interrogation 'What can we do?' works somehow as a waiver of liability, inasmuch as local inequalities reflect wider societal differences, from which the institute cannot escape.

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Finally, another issue identified at the IGOT analysis is the lack of awareness about the existence of a gender-related problem in management bodies, which have been expressed precisely by some members of the management bodies. Nevertheless, it is also recognized that there is a clear tendency to fill the management positions with men (bias), but no specific justification is given. There is a perception that management positions have been offered to women, but that they declined taking up these leadership tasks. Wording is very telling and can expose deep-seated assumptions that might come to surface (or that are already very evident): expressions such as 'tend'/'tendency', '[the numbers] are what they are', or 'we still have a traditional inheritance from our country' often reveal arguments that have been naturalized by participants, which have to do with the roles, skills and capabilities relating to women and to men.

Regarding decision-making processes, in particular the one of appointment of a Dean, the process is well defined, with clear stages and procedures that are mandatory to follow in order to make the appointment. It is important to state that all the processes are described in national regulations, as it is a public entity. Therefore, the influence of institutional leaders on these regulated procedures is limited, although this regulation is not free of incorporating gendered elements on itself.

2.2. UL

As in the case of IGOT, the Faculty of Arts of the University of Ljubljana faces gender imbalances at both University and Faculty level. In this case, the disequilibrium in the top management at Faculty level is clear: in the 2009-2019 period, there have been thirteen men as vice-deans versus only five women. In middle management positions, in contrast, there is gender balance, and sometimes even more women than men.

Apart from the quantitative data showed in the Institutional Assessment, the qualitative information reveals a tension between gender equality and academic achievements, understanding the relationship between them as mutually exclusive. For the interviewees, the inclusion of the gender perspective in career progression goes against a merit-based appointment process, which is conceptually the preferred one.

The overall impression is that the interviewees have basic understanding of and are in principle in favour of gender equality. They also see some areas for intervention, such as progression in academic titles, work life balance, gender sensitive language or the need for sex-disaggregated data. They also expressed a certain level of sensitivity towards gender equality, but interviews also reveal the need for further gender awareness raising activities.

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In general, none of the interviewees see objective, structural conditions in accessing leadership positions as a challenge to gender equality. Although some of them identified institutional resistances, they expressed support for gender equality and recognised the potential for change they have as a person in a leadership position.

Nevertheless, resistances, in the form of scepticism, but mostly on account of the lack of knowledge on the matter, were expressed while discussing possible equality mechanisms for assuring gender equality in leadership positions, such as quotas. According to interviewees such mechanisms (beyond the issues of equality in leadership) are still perceived as unjust, even by the women themselves – due to favouring women on account of lowering the standards/criteria.

Leadership positions are seen as demanding due to increased inability to balance work and non-work related activities, and also due to pursuing academic careers in parallel. Most of the interviewees at least partially understand their personal productivity in terms of masculine perception and recognise the burden of balancing family and private life with the demands of the job – as part of structural conditions. On the other hand, a presence of solidarity and collaboration is detected, which in individual professional practices deviate from standard each-for-himself individualism, stemming from masculine codes traditionally inscribed in the structure of academic institutions.

Finally, regarding decision-making processes, the size of the faculty and the specificities of the leadership and related processes, is seen as a factor adding more complexity to the procedures (i.e. there are less options when selecting candidates) and, as a consequence, to the achievement of a gender balance. In the particular case of the process of appointment of the Dean, as it is an elected position, the process is well defined, with clear stages and little room for biases. The only possible bias could come from the informal rule that states that only full professors can apply for the position (the share of women full professors is lower) and from women's perceived self-exclusion.

2.3. OBU

Data reported in the Institutional Report show that women are generally well represented across all committees and decision-making groups, and this reflects a university commitment to diversity of representation. However, there is less consistency in visible ethnic diversity and representation of self-identified BAME (Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic) staff. This is being monitored to help identify gaps and drive change. As committee memberships are drawn from existing leadership and management positions, their composition tends to reproduce the profile of the prevailing university hierarchy which may take some time to change.

Being part of, contributing to and having responsibilities at a committee or sub-committee were identified as important channels that one can embark on to progress to leadership roles and responsibilities. It was felt that opportunities to shadow existing committee members and

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deputising would allow for more committee participation for women and also BAME staff, increasing their participation.

A good practice was identified in terms of the diversity of the groups that formally contribute to decision-making: Structures where an LGBTQ+ planning group (which includes representation from the university HR function as well as from different groups such as BAME) is consulted on changes to university internal structures and processes. This allows for some consideration of staff and student needs arising from a range of characteristics, in addition to gender.

With regard to qualitative information, there is a concern about gendered patterns of inclusion when appointing new leaders. There is a risk of assigning roles in 'softer' areas to women (HR, Students experience, Staff Experience). In addition, people in top positions tend to come from a more scientific background instead of people with a social science or humanities studies background, with the risk of not understanding the language of addressing gender inequality.

Several interviewees argued that issues remain for BAME staff, particularly BAME women. This perceived lack of BAME individuals at senior levels is supported by statistical evidence outlined in the institutional report. There are also perceptions that there is poor BAME representation in staff generally. In addition, there are few 'out' LGBTQ+ women in senior positions. In recent years, a 'promotion roadshow' has been delivered which has shown great success with increasing transparency in processes for career progression and understanding of how these systems work. These have benefitted both women and men.

The general feeling is that the University supports women across faculties and directorates to participate in the national [Aurora](#) initiative for women in higher education, with connection to the internal network of Aurora alumnae at Oxford Brookes. There is also in-house mentoring support. Mentoring for career progression is, therefore, identified to be available by OBU staff, although several interviewees confirmed that general understanding and knowledge about the in-house mentoring programme is "not as good as it could be: [because we] don't have the interventions in place". Therefore, take-up is not as high as it should be. Mentoring is felt to be particularly important for women. One leader discussed his involvement as a mentor, stating that he had initially felt that gender equality "is a subject by women, for women". However, he discussed this with senior colleagues who argued differently and then "came on board and now is on 3rd cohort mentoring women, as some women prefer a man as a mentor and though that's uncomfortable for some, it's what they want because 'that's where the power lies'".

People who were interviewed at OBU indicated that the institution also has a number of highly visible senior women within the university. These women were identified as good role models, and an indicator that it is possible for women to succeed within the institution. However, the existence of these role models was limited in the case of BAME women, an issue that may deter

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BAME candidates from seeking career progression (particularly clarifying is the sentence: “You can’t be what you can’t see”).

The observation that women are well-represented at senior levels was in respect of both women professors and in the most senior leadership positions. In some faculties, there is a near equal split between professorial women and men. As data in the Institutional Report also reveals, however, women are over-represented in lower grades (particularly grade 6 which is dominated by administrative positions). This suggests that there are issues related to women’s access to leadership and decision-making positions which may have implications for the ‘pipeline’. Women are also over-represented in terms of part-time work, and this was acknowledged as being a potential constraint to career progression for some roles which are less suited to part-time work. A stigma seems to exist around working part-time, in that people believe senior roles cannot be part-time, which was also felt to be widespread in managerial attitudes and part of the prevailing culture of the organisation. However, some argued that senior roles can successfully be carried out on a part-time basis, though there is a need for some flexibility in those roles.

In addition, at faculty level some areas show a drop-off of women at levels leading into professorship, for example at reader level in humanities and social sciences. Other areas are entirely dominated by one gender, for example, mechanical engineering by men and nursing by women. It was also argued that there is a widespread expectation for women at a senior level “to be superhuman and selfless in some way”. Expectations on women to fulfil these roles were felt to be based on stereotypes which need to be challenged by the institution.

Finally, difficulties in returning to a research career following breaks for pregnancy, maternity and childcare/other caring responsibilities were seen to be an obstacle to women’s progression. One factor which was seen as helping with this is the existence of group coaching and informal mentors which has been put in place.

When assessing the process of appointing a Dean, several biases in the selection process could be identified. It is worth noting that the process is seen as a general hiring process, as it is not a requirement to belong to the institution to be appointed as a Dean (with the associated position of Vice-Chancellor). Consequently, self-exclusion biases or biases in the selection and interviewing process could be present in all the intervening committees.

2.4. SU

Sabanci University also faces gender imbalance, both in some faculties’ bodies as well as in the highest decision-making, being the widest imbalance in the latter. If we examine statistical data, at University level, in all the bodies with the exception of the Director’s level, the presence of women is less than 40 per cent.

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All interviews started by asking what interviewees think has been the role of gender in their career choice and paths, or whether they think it has a role at all. They were all pleasantly surprised by the question, indicated that this was not something they had thought about, or had to think about before, and as one interviewee expressed, the very fact that he did not have to think about this is quite telling in terms of the role of gender in shaping one's career.

All interviewed leaders have positive and affirmative perspectives towards women's role in society and academic life, and gender equality in general. Their sensitivity to issues regarding gender equality/inequality in society and work life stems from family backgrounds, i.e. growing up in egalitarian families with both parents working, academic backgrounds, i.e. receiving a high school education that embraced values such as inclusion and anti-discrimination. Having strong women as role models, including mothers, sisters, friends and colleagues was also mentioned in the interviews.

They all agree that there are obstacles to women's career advancement in any sector in general, however, these obstacles do not exist at Sabanci University. It is possible to say that all interviewees contend that Sabanci University, as a private university in Istanbul with a strong academic track record and international prominence, has to be set aside from the rest of Turkey. Although leaders identify barriers to women's advancement in their careers such as glass ceilings, access to leadership positions and others, they do not believe that such barriers exist at SU. They describe SU as a privileged environment. Many interviewees believe that Sabanci University has a "culture of equality," and a background of talking about gender issues.

The fact that currently, all higher administrators are men with the exception of one woman dean is interpreted as a coincidence by all interviewees. They explained that the picture was different a few years ago, and the fact that all vice presidents and two thirds of all deans are men today is only coincidental and that they were chosen because they do their jobs well. However, they all believe that it is important to have more women in decision-making committees, to improve the situation and to make sure that different perspectives are included.

The analysis concludes that potentially the biggest resistance to change will be directed towards any proposed affirmative action policies. Although no such policies currently exist at SU, even when they were not asked about their opinion about positive discrimination, almost all respondents mentioned it themselves and express a negative attitude towards it. Five out of six refer to the meritocracy discourse and express a binary opposition between merit and positive discrimination; two respondents have slightly open but quiet hesitant attitudes towards affirmative action.

However, some informal practices are being carried out in the appointment processes, such as making sure that all committees in the Research and Graduate Policies Directorate have women.

SU also identified several informal factors limiting selection for management bodies and committees:

- Even distribution of the workload: assuring that is not the same people that take part in all the commissions or management activities.
- Preference for Turkish-speaking candidates: unconsciously, there is a preference to Turkish speakers, as they state the conversation in the bodies are more fluid.

Decision-making processes are seen as not so transparent and inclusive, particularly due to the fact that the selection criteria are not public. The deans are selected by the Rector and approved by the Board of Trustees. Some Rectors have informally consulted the faculty members before these appointments, but this is not regular practice. The Rector is the ultimate decision-maker in this decision-making process.

Finally, the analysis shows that while the leaders can identify areas for improvement regarding gender equality, or become aware of them during the course of the interview, only two out of the six interviewees used active language and identified themselves as change makers.

2.5. ETAg

ETAg also experiences gender imbalances in women's representation in top positions, an issue which is currently addressed due to a personal boost of the Director General of ETAg to the appointment of women in the bodies where there are more underrepresentation.

The interviewees were asked about their general perception of gender equality in Estonia, with similar answers: they believe that we should pay more attention to this topic, although some of them consider that it is not the most important problem. There was the perception of a lack of training about unconscious biases regarding gender issues. However, people inside the institution did not see this topic as a priority, as they recognized that there are other high importance topics to talk about and limited resources to deal with all of them.

Inside the organisation, both interviewees perceived that the imbalance is different when talking about their own workforce or about the expert panels and evaluation committees. In the case of the workforce, men are the underrepresented gender. However, in the case of expert panels, women faced a big imbalance in the past, reaching parity only in their last composition. In any case, no active policy has been done to reach this parity, but it is a matter of growing consciousness in the whole scientific world and RPOs nominating more women for committees.

The ETAg, and Estonian society as a whole, also displays a high resistance to quotas as a positive affirmative measure (in particular, it is said that Estonian society is not prepared for quotas). Linked to that resistance, several people interviewed have the perception that time will solve

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the situations of imbalance, due to the incorporation of women to the top positions in science (which is the pool of people from which the institution selects its members). Along the interviews, gender imbalance was attributed to 'natural' differences between women and men, demonstrating the different levels of understanding of gender equality that exist in the organisation.

A Research Funding Organization can play an important role in fostering gender mainstreaming in research and development. In this sense, the introduction of gender aspects in all research proposals is perceived as difficult, in particular in STEM areas

Finally, regarding the appointment of top authorities of ETAg, due to its nature of public agency, the appointments come directly and discretionarily from the government of Estonia. And in the case of the Expert Panels, again comes from outside the organisation, as the estonian higher education and research institutions are asked to make the choices of experts by themselves.

2.6. UDEUSTO

The Institutional Assessment at DEUSTO suggested paying attention to several issues regarding leadership and decision-making.

Exploring the perceptions the respondents have about the reasons underlying the unequal distribution of leadership positions according to gender, asking about possible obstacles or challenges that women may face in access to these positions. Some voices claim roundly that “women have more difficulties than men in accessing positions of leadership in the society, everywhere”. Others, usually men, state they do not know “where the brake is” or claim that women “have equal opportunities”, as “the university seeks “that profiles that can better perform those purposes without taking gender into account”.

Nevertheless, addressing this issue, the respondents’ speeches often pointed out the workload and the time dedication that involve management positions, aspects that are in conflict with family roles socially attributed to women and with the values and codes internalised by these.

The tension between work and family demands is expressed with higher anxiety and challenge in women. Some of them point out that the difficulty of access to management positions lies in “the ongoing effort that needs to be done to keep the professional and personal life balance”. Their speeches help us understand how the internalised construction of femininity, linked to the care of the children and the family, in interaction with a labour structure designed on the basis of the masculine traditional experience (exempt from the social mandate to care, entirely available for the job), can mediate in the decisions of women with family responsibilities in the assumption of management positions. All this appears to come off the perception that women who surpass the “glass ceiling” are women with a more advanced age or with no reproductive responsibilities.

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Another issue that emerges in the narratives is the disaffection or distance experienced by women toward leadership roles, they perceive and live it as something foreign to them. Once again, the positions and gender attributions shape, often in invisible ways, attitudes towards these positions. Thus, the construct of femininity not built as leaders can whip up fears and insecurities in decision-making about the access to these positions, which requires “emotional stability, baggage and support”.

The feeling of insecurity or inability to access these positions, along with the lack of valuation or merit associated to their own position - the so-called “Impostor syndrome” - synthesizes the contradiction between the traditional femininity construction (such as lower or secondary – “the unessential”-) and the leadership roles, traditionally dominated by men.

There are a number of statements that mention the incidence of “culture” or “tradition” as an obstacle to women inclusion in senior management positions. In particular, it points out the difficulty of a woman holding the Rector position, as the UDEUSTO is a Jesuit university (a religious order for men), which sets up a “glass ceiling” difficult to transfer, despite the – relatively recent– regulatory change that would allow a woman to occupy the position.

Beyond the assertions that women have the same opportunities, when electing senior positions according to the individual merits, the underlying narratives elicits the rise of pitfalls of diverse nature that contribute to the “scissors-effect” (that is, while the participation of men increases, that of women decreases as the academic levels move towards the top ranks) detected in the Institutional Assessment. Structural obstacles, such as the design of the leadership positions from a masculine perspective (traditionally exempt of reproductive responsibilities), are linked to symbolic walls, as the interiorisation of the construction of femininity as a caregiver and not as a leader, to what it is added the society’s and institution’s culture and inertia.

The collected speeches agree highlighting that, in recent years, changes in favour of equality opportunity and women’s greater access to leadership positions have occurred in the UDEUSTO. However, talking about the possibility of implementing quotas frequently awakens attitudes of rejection and resistance among the people consulted, especially among men. Expressions like “I don’t share it at all”, “I don’t like them”, “I don’t really agree” are repeated in the speeches collected. Their arguments point out that the selection criteria should be the merit and performance, as it may be counter-productive to generate, on the women who ascend, the feeling that they are “trophy wife” or “a quota”, or that she might pose problems when the reverse situation occurs in the future or in certain sectors. On top of this, the belief that equality will come as part of a natural process of social evolution, led to the perception that the measure is not necessary. By contrast, several other discourses, despite expressing an initial opposition to the measure, claim that it may be a necessary tool against this inequality situation that exists in the management bodies of the university. The mentoring and counselling of women elicits, in general, larger adhesions between people consulted.

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Likewise, to overcome the structural conditions that hinder work-life balance and favour men in senior positions at the university –and generically, in institutions of our environment– some discourses mark the need to rethink the management model of the institution and, in particular, the long working and inflexible schedules linked to these positions.

Regarding leadership models, the idea that women and men have “different sensitivities” and a “separated” leadership which can be “complementary” is frequently repeated in the stories of the people consulted. These also pointed that “there are common principles” and “there’s everything” in both collectives, in a manner that one cannot speak about “exclusive features”. Some people placed in the extremes noted that it is “another way of looking at” the face of those who, without denying the difference, suspect that this “will not have a great magnitude”. Although the manifestations of the people consulted differ in their intensity, they speak about feminine leadership as characterised by traits such as empathy, care, moodiness, patience, dialogue, and the more global vision, against a masculine leadership described as more task-oriented and dynamic steering.

Finally, despite the fact that the consulted people considered that the UDEUSTO, through its historical journey and religious link, had traditionally decided on men leaders, they support the inherent Ignatian leadership of this Jesuit institution promotes listening, dialogue and caring for people. Many voices link these characteristics to a stereotypically “more feminine”, “inclusive” leadership model. Furthermore, in general, there is a claim to be placed with ease in this leadership ideology, which tries to seek “a balance” between task orientation and people’s care.

Regarding the process of a Dean appointment, it is important to differentiate between the formal process (the one contained in the general statutes of the institution) and the informal activities. These informal activities mainly consist of informal conversations between Rector and faculty members prior to the beginning of the process to gather as many opinions as possible about potential candidates. In these informal conversations, principal biases may appear related to the type of questions asked and the lack of structure of the interview. Furthermore, the little possibility of spontaneous candidature could also be considered as a risk of bias in the process.

3. Employees perception: Questionnaire Analysis

In order to complement the quantitative indicators, as well as the qualitative information, data were collected in each institution around leadership and decision-making processes from a gender perspective. To do so, a questionnaire was administered to all the employees of the GEPs.

The questionnaire is composed of different sections, each of them aiming at a different area directly or indirectly connected to leadership challenges and the goal of promoting women in decision-making positions. The following sections were included:

1. Demographics
2. General Values
3. Work-Life Balance
4. About Supervisor

1. DEMOGRAPHICS

In total, the sample size included 445 individuals (65% women, 32% men and 1% non-binary). Of these 61% were Teaching and Research Staff, while 39% were Administrative Staff and Professional Services. The questionnaire reached a minimum sample size of 30 participants per institution. For one partner (ETAg), due to their small size, they reached 20% of their employees with less than 30 responses. The highest number of respondents came from UDEUSTO, with 283 respondents.

The most frequent age range in the sample is 41-50 years, with an average of 8.19 years (SD=7.61) in their actual professional category and 12.45 (SD=9.91) years at the institution. Slightly more than half of the sample is composed of employees without management responsibilities, and a further third from middle management. Top management was the category least represented, yet still represent over one in ten of survey respondents.

Which is your professional category?	
Employee without management responsibilities	53,6%
Middle Management	35,3%
Top Management (Dean, Vice-Dean, Member of the Board of Directors, Head of Unit...)	11,2%

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Finally, regarding their domestic structure, more than a half of the sample lived with her or his partner and/or dependent children. The average number of dependent children (i.e., less than 18 years) for the employees in the sample is 1.12 (SD=0.96), and the average number of non-dependent children is 0.49 (SD=0.78).

Which domestic structure applies to you?	
I live alone	12,8%
I live with my partner	60,0%
I live with my dependent children	52,2%
I live with elder dependent relatives	6,4%
I share living space with other people (none of the above)	4,9%

2. GENERAL VALUES

INDIVIDUAL TRAITS (COMMUNION AND AGENCY)

Once some basic demographics had been collected, the first section aimed at understanding individual traits. In particular, we included a first section looking at the personal traits of communality and agency, as they represent two-dimensional dispositions of gendered individual behavior and social judgement under which many other individual dispositions can be subsumed (Abele & Wojciszke, 2007). Communion is defined as traits that focus on social relationships, and agency captures self-oriented traits related to pursuit of one's goals.

A relevant number of communion-related traits are important at work and in particular in relation to leadership in most contemporary models of organisational functioning, and thus the communal dimension and its gendered nature is gaining particular relevance with the growing relevance of teamwork and cooperation (see Gartzia & van Knippenberg, 2016; Gartzia & van Engen, 2012). Indeed, research has repeatedly pointed to sex differences in communion-related personality dimensions (Schmitt, Realo, Voracek & Allik, 2008; Costa, Terracciano & McCrae, 2001) and we therefore included these traits to observe any potential differences in our samples that may help explain communal vs. agentic dispositions in the organisations.

In this regard, employees are asked about their personal traits by means of the Personal Attributes Questionnaire (Ward et al, 2006). This scale is composed of twelve items that refers

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either to an agentic or a communal trait. Both subscales show good reliability (Cronbach’s alphas of 0.705 and 0.810 respectively). Each item was rated from 1=not at all to 5=completely true.

Agentic Traits	Competitive Daring Adventurous Aggressive Dominant Courageous
Communal Traits	Loving Understanding Kind Sensitive Sympathetic Affectionate

Figure 1 shows the results for the agency and the communal sub-scales by sex (note that non-binary respondents have been excluded from these analysis thourought the document, due to the small sample size):

Figure 1. Agentic and Communal traits by sex. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (completely true).

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As shown in the Figure, whereas agency traits are displayed to a similar level by both men and women, communal traits are present to a higher extent in women. This last difference is statistically significant at a 95 percent confidence level.

If we look at the data grouping the sample by the professional group of the respondent, the observed differences were not relevant from a gender perspective, with only slightly higher scores in all dimensions for the Administrative and Professional Services staff.

Figure 2. Agentic and Communal traits by professional group. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (completely true).

Figure 3. Agentic and Communal traits by professional category. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (completely true).

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In order to see whether the agentic and communal differences remain across occupational domains, an ANOVA with a post hoc Tukey test was performed. In this figure, the breakdown by category is presented. The only significant difference at a 95% confidence level was found between Middle Management and Top Management in the communal traits. Lower communion among top managers is the main difference across all respondents, pointing to a lower prevalence of communal traits as managerial responsibilities become higher.

LEADERSHIP ASPIRATIONS

Because leadership aspirations can help explain potential differences in promotion processes and the number of women and men in leadership positions, we examined potential differences in leadership aspirations in our samples. One may argue that greater numbers of men in managerial positions is due simply to their greater individual disposition to engage in leadership positions in the company. However, similar scores from women and men in leadership aspirations would point to other factors beyond sex differences in management beyond individual aspirations.

In our samples, leadership aspirations were assessed using the Career Aspiration Scale (Gray, 2007), composed of eight items that should be rated from 1=not at all true to 6=totally true. The scale shows acceptable reliability, with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.692. Items included in the scale are:

Leadership Aspirations	<p>I hope to become a leader in my career field</p> <p>When I am established in my career, I would like to manage other employees</p> <p>I do not plan to devote energy to getting promoted in the organisation or business I am working in*</p> <p>When I am established in my career, I would like to train others</p> <p>I hope to move up through any organisation or business I work in</p> <p>Attaining leadership status in my career is not that important to me*</p>
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**Reverse scoring items*

Figure 4 shows how overall leadership aspirations are high, with no significant differences between women and men.

Figure 4. Leadership Aspirations by sex. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 6 (totally true).

As in the previous section, a disaggregation of the data by professional group provides the following information, showing that leadership aspirations are slightly lower among academic staff:

Figure 5. Leadership Aspirations by professional group. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 6 (totally true).

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OVERALL SATISFACTION AT WORK

Overall satisfaction at work was measured by means of the Brief Index of Affective Job Satisfaction (Thompson and Phua, 2012), rating its four items from 1=not at all true to 5=totally true. The scale shows high reliability (Cronbach’s alpha 0.769). These items are:

Satisfaction at work	<p>I find real enjoyment in my job</p> <p>I definitely dislike my job*</p> <p>I am fairly well satisfied with my job</p> <p>I feel dissatisfied with my present job*</p>
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**Reverse scoring items*

The following figure illustrates how employees found generally high levels of satisfaction at work, with no statistically significant differences between women and men - they show similar levels of work satisfaction.

Figure 6. Satisfaction at work by sex. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (totally true).

Looking at the data by professional group, people from Administrative and Professional Services show slightly less satisfaction at work. Both differences are statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

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Figure 7. Satisfaction at work by professional group. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (totally true).

Finally, if we look at the data disaggregated by professional category, the only difference that is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level is the one between employees without specific responsibilities and top managers.

Figure 8. Satisfaction at work by professional category. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (totally true).

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MODERN SEXISM IN SOCIETY

Participants were asked to indicate to what extent, in their opinion, sexist attitudes prevail in our society. To this end, the Modern Sexism Inventory (Swim et al, 1995) was provided, rating its eight items in a 1=totally disagree to 5=totally agree scale (Cronbach’s alpha 0.766). Higher scores indicate greater beliefs that sexism is still prevalent in social values and discourse in general. Items in this scale include:

Sexism	Discrimination against women is no longer a problem in my country* Women often miss out on good jobs due to sexual discrimination It is rare to see women treated in a sexist manner on television* On average, people in our society treat husbands and wives equally* Society has reached the point where women and men have equal opportunities for achievement* It is easy to understand the anger of women’s groups in my country It is easy to understand why women’s groups are still concerned about societal limitations of women’s opportunities Over the past few years, the government and news media have been showing more concern about the treatment of women than is warranted by women’s actual experiences*
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*Reverse scoring items

*Reverse scoring items are already calculated in their positive form in the figure

Figure 9. Sexism items by sex. Average From 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree).

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Results in Figure 9 show how women's and men's opinions differ. Women's scores are higher than men's, meaning that they are more likely to perceive that sexism is still present in society. Across respondents, there is a high level of agreement that sexism remains an issue in our society. No statistically significant differences emerged between Academic and Administrative and Professional Services staff.

3. WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND FAMILY-SUPPORTIVE ORIENTATIONS IN THE ORGANIZATION

Because domestic work is still one of the major challenges for working women, who still hold greater domestic burdens that result in a “motherhood penalty” with very negative consequences for their career (Alon et al., 2020), the second section of the questionnaire was designed to understand work-life balance issues.

The literature has examined at least two potential barriers related to the use of work-life balance initiatives at work: the managers' attitude towards care and the corporate culture (Fritz & Van Knippenberg, 2017). This is because it is important for the effectiveness of work-life initiatives to create an environment in which work-life initiatives are widely accepted (Fritz & Van Knippenberg, 2017). Regarding the first barrier, Escot et al. (2012) highlighted the importance of the concept “female bias in reconciliation”, defined as “the perception held by managers of organisations and fellow-workers that the need for reconciling, and the family-work conflict, are questions specifically relating to women and not so much with men” (Bustelo & Peterson, 2005; Holter, 2007). This is consistent with the study carried out by Haas & Hwang (2007), who analysed the organisational culture and companies' responsiveness to parenting, concluding that few companies see taking parental leave as positive and less than half report support from supervisors and co-workers (see also Gartzia, Sánchez-Vidal & Cegarra-Leiva, 2018).

Humbert et al. (2018) also recognized the central role that top leaders play in affecting gender equality at organisational level through their ability to shape organisational cultures and practices (Schein, 2010; Kelan & Wratil, 2018). In the same sense, Konrad & Linnehan (1995) found a positive relationship between leaders' attitudes and the effectiveness of gender equality actions.

In addition to managers' attitude, in order to improve the conditions for using work-life initiatives, a change in the organisational culture toward a more family-friendly culture is necessary (Vinkenburg et al., 2015). The organisational culture appears to be a corporate barrier that creates a gap between the theoretical rights and the use of the leaves by men (Belope-Nguema et al, 2018).

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Responding to these concerns, participants in our sample were asked about their perceptions of to what extent work-life balance practices are commonly accepted in the organisation (in other words, a work-life balance oriented organisational culture). Additionally, to capture the potential specificities of perceptions about leaders’ beliefs, participants were also asked to indicate to what extent work-life balance practices are commonly accepted by their direct supervisor/line manager.

Two scales were applied to capture these perceptions. On the one hand, the Reconciliation Bias scale (Belope-Nguema et al, 2018) measures to what extent an employee perceives a bias against fathers’ work-life balance measures in the company . This scale was applied twice in the questionnaire, once for the company and another time for the supervisor. It is composed of five items, measured in a five point scale (not at all true/totally true). In both cases, reliability is high (Cronbach’s alpha 0.922 and 0.902 respectively).

Items for this scale are:

Reconciliation Bias	<p>The need to balance work and family life is conceived as something that concerns mainly the female staff of the company, and not so much the masculine one.</p> <p>It is considered more ‘natural’ for a mother to apply for a paid leave, unpaid leave or a reduction of working hours to care for small children, than for the father to apply for it.</p> <p>A mother/father who uses the work-life balance measures available in the company (working hours reduction, etc.) is seen as an uncompetitive and unambitious worker.</p> <p>A mother/father who uses the work-life balance measures available in the company (working hours reduction, etc.) is seen as a rather weak and insecure worker.</p> <p>A mother/father who uses the work-life balance measures available in the company (working hours reduction, etc.) is often seen as someone who ‘sneaks off’ from work for some other purpose.</p>
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On the other hand, FSOP - the Family-Supportive Organizational Perceptions Scale (Allen, 2001) - measures to what extent the employee perceives the work environment family supportive. The scale consists of fourteen items, ranging from 1=not true about my organisation to 5=totally true about my organisation. The reliability of the scale is good (Cronbach’s alpha 0.918). Items include:

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FSOP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Work should be the primary priority in a person's life* 2. Long hours inside the office are the way to achieve advancement* 3. It is best to keep family matters separate from work* 4. It is considered taboo to talk about life outside of work* 5. Expressing involvement and interest in nonwork matters is viewed as healthy 6. Employees who are highly committed to their personal lives cannot be highly committed to their work* 7. Attending to personal needs, such as taking time off for sick children, is frowned upon* 8. Employees should keep their personal problems at home* 9. The way to advance in this company is to keep nonwork matters out of the workplace* 10. Individuals who take time off to attend to personal matters are not committed to their work* 11. It is assumed that the most productive employees are those who put their work before their family life* 12. Employees are given ample opportunity to perform both their job and their personal responsibilities well 13. Offering employees flexibility in completing their work is viewed as a strategic way of doing business 14. The ideal employee is the one who is available 24 hours a day*
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*Reverse scoring items

Figure 10. Reconciliation Bias and FSOP by sex. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (totally true).

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Figure 10 shows how the different scales follow the same trend. In all of them women perceive both the organisation and the supervisor as biased when referring to work-life balance significantly higher than men. Moreover, the FSOP scale confirms this pattern, as women believe they work in a less family friendly environment than men. However, it is important to note that both women and men score high in FSOP, pointing to perceptions of the organisations as generally family supportive, whereas perceptions about the Reconciliation Bias are represented at a moderate level.

In the case of Academic versus Administrative and Professional Services staff, the difference is only statistically significant at a 95% confidence level for the FSOP scale, as it can be shown in Figure 11. Both groups perceive Reconciliation Bias, as well as FSOP as moderate.

Figure 11. Reconciliation Bias and FSOP by professional group. Average From 1 (not at all true) to 5 (totally true).

Individual work-family conflict was also assessed by means of the Netemeyer et al (1990) scale (Cronbach’s alpha 0.939). Composed of five items, each item is rated from 1=totally disagree to 7=totally agree, capturing the extent to which each of the statements are true or not for the participant.

	<p>The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life</p> <p>The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfil family responsibilities</p>
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WFC	<p>Things I want to do at home do not get done because of the demands my job puts on me</p> <p>My job produces strain that makes it difficult to fulfil family duties</p> <p>Due to work-related duties, I have to make changes to my plans for family activities</p>
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The results show that, overall, there are no gender differences in the way in which work interferes with work in the private sphere. Both women and men perceive moderate effects in this variable (nearly four points out of seven). In the same sense, at a 95% confidence level, no statistically significant differences are found between Academic and Administrative and Professional Services staff nor employees and managers. In this case, they also perceive a moderate level, with an average of 4.14 out of seven for Academic staff and 3.59 for Administrative and Professional Services staff.

Figure 12. WFC by sex. Average From 1 (totally disagree) to 7 (totally agree).

However, we can find statistically significant differences when looking at the data by professional category. In this sense, by using an ANOVA with a post hoc Tukey test, the only significant difference at a 95% confidence level is the difference between employees without management responsibilities and top management.

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Figure 13. WFC by professional category. Average From 1 (totally disagree) to 7 (totally agree).

ACCEPTANCE OF QUOTAS AS A CHANGE MECHANISM

The under-representation of women as leaders remains salient both in academia and in other organisational contexts. One of the measures that have proven to be effective to redress this imbalance is the implementation of quotas (Storvik and Teigen, 2010). But at the same time, this practice is highly controversial, provoking resistances on its execution (Humbert et al., 2018; Terjesen et al., 2015)

As a final aspect in the section, therefore, participants were asked about their perception about quotas. In particular, they were asked the following questions: *From 0 (Nothing) to 10 (Totally), are you in favor of establishing quotas in management positions?; From 1 (Very negatively) to 4 (Very positively), how do you think the implementation of these quotas would affect your organisation?; and From 1 (Very negatively) to 4 (Very positively), how do you think the implementation of these quotas would affect your own professional development?.*

As it can be concluded from the data presented in Figure 14, women are significantly more likely to be in favor of quotas.

Figure 14. Acceptance of quotas by sex. Average From 0 (Nothing) to 10 (Totally).

In addition, their scores are also higher in relation to the belief that quotas can have positive effects both for the organisation and their own professional development.

Figure 15. Perceived effects of quotas by sex. Average From 1 (Very negative) to 4 (Very positive).

There are no statistically significant differences in these items between Academic and Administrative and Professional Services staff. Both groups are moderately in favor of quotas,

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and both believe that quotas will affect negatively to the organisation and their professional development.

Figure 16. Acceptance of quotas by professional group. Average From 0 (Nothing) to 10 (Totally).

Figure 17. Perceived effects of quotas by professional group. Average From 1 (Very negatively) to 4 (Very positively).

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The only difference that is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level (by means of an ANOVA with a post hoc Tukey test) is the difference between employees without management responsibilities and the top management in the item regarding the effects of quotas on professional development.

Figure 18. Acceptance of quotas by professional category. Average From 0 (Nothing) to 10 (Totally).

Figure 19. Perceived effects of quotas by professional category. Average From 1 (Very negatively) to 4 (Very positively).

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4. ABOUT SUPERVISOR (LEADERSHIP STYLES)

The last section refers to the perceptions about one's direct supervisor at work. In order to complete it, participants were asked to think about the person that supervises their work in their daily organizational life. To start, several demographic questions were asked about the supervisor, followed by employees' evaluations of these managers' leadership styles.

In total, the sample size of supervisors included 427 individuals (47.3% women, 51.2% men and 1.4% prefer not to say). The most frequent age range in the sample is 51-60 years, with an average of 9.34 years ($SD=8.60$) meeting this person and 4.01 ($SD=4.25$) years being his or her leader.

Regarding the percentage of time in contact, participants reported being in physical contact with their supervisor an average of 12.85% ($SD=21.70$) of the time of the working day, whereas 10.19% of the time were they on average ($SD=17.55$) in virtual contact. Finally, an average of 49.51% ($SD=32.45$) of the decisions affecting their work are taken by this supervisor.

Leadership styles are important influences not only for organisational effectiveness (Yukl, 2010), but also for gender equality. Indeed, to a great extent the interest in women as leaders has traditionally focused on whether they lead in a more communal (i.e., people oriented) way than men, consistent with "female advantage" proposals (see Eagly, Gartzia & Carli, 2012 for a critical review). For instance, there is meta-analytical evidence that women leaders generally display a more democratic and less autocratic leadership style than men managers (Eagly & Johnson, 1990). However, sex-related differences are generally smaller in the gender-stereotypical tendencies for men to be more task-oriented and women more interpersonally oriented. These differences are also generally smaller than the more persistent communal-agentive difference usually found in relation to personality traits (presented in the first section), given the greater stability of personality traits compared to more specific leadership behaviors performed at work. Importantly, also, these differences tend to be stronger in nonmanagerial samples (like students), given the strong pressures that women often encounter to behave in stereotypically masculine ways when they engage in managerial roles (Koenig et al., 2011).

With these ideas in mind, in this section we included questions about employees' perceptions of the leadership styles displayed by their direct supervisors. We used the Mentor and Task-Orientation subscales of the Competing Values Management Practices Survey (Quinn, 1998). Each of these two scales are composed of four items, and show strong reliability (Cronbach's alpha 0.966 and 0.890 respectively). The Mentor dimension refers to leadership behaviors focused on the development of employees via an empathic orientation, facilitating opportunities for training and skills development. In contrast, the task-orientation dimension represents the extent to which the leader focuses on tasks and goals more directly, emphasizing the work to be done (Quinn & Rohrbaugh, 1983).

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The following table contains the items of each of the dimensions.

Mentor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Listen to the personal problems of group members Treat each individual in a sensitive, caring way Show concern for the needs of group members Show empathy and concern in dealing with group members
Task-Orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus on results for the group Ensure the group delivers on stated goals Push the group to meet objectives Emphasize the group's achievement of stated purposes

Another three leadership styles were added to the analysis from Podsakoff et al (1990): two transformational leadership styles (*Intellectual Stimulation* - that challenges employees to re-examine some or their assumptions about their work and rethink how it can be performed - and *Individualized Consideration* - behavior of the leaders that indicates that he or she respects followers and is concerned about their personal feelings and needs) and one transactional leadership style (*Contingent Reward*). Each of these dimensions was composed of three items, and the scales show good reliability (Cronbach's alpha 0.920, 0,951 and 0.974 respectively). All of the items were rated in a 1=not at all to 7=totally scale. The items are as follows:

Intellectual Stimulation	<p>This manager...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges me to think about old problems in new ways Has ideas that have forced me to rethink some things that I have never questioned before Has challenged me to rethink some of my basic assumptions about my work
Individualized Consideration	<p>This manager...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considers my personal feelings before acting Behaves in a manner which is thoughtful of my personal needs Sees that the interests of employees are given due consideration
Contingent Reward	<p>This manager...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commends me when I do a better than average job Acknowledges improvement in my quality of work Personally compliments me when I do outstanding work

With regard to the prevalence of each leadership style, *Mentor* style is perceived by employees as to be displayed with higher intensity by the 62.3% of the leaders, followed by Task orientation (58.7%) and provision of contingent rewards (58.6%). On the opposite, the less displayed leadership styles are Individualized Consideration (52.8%) and Intellectual Stimulation (37%).

Looking at differences in how women and men are perceived to display these styles in leadership roles, results show that participants rated women more positively in all communion-related leadership styles compared to men. In particular, statistically significant differences appeared in the *Individualized Consideration* and *Mentor* dimensions, whereby female leaders were rated as significantly more interpersonally oriented leaders. For the other dimensions, no statistically significant sex differences emerged.

Figure 20. Leadership Styles by sex of the supervisor. Average From 1 (not at all) to 7 (totally).

In further inspection of these results, we looked at potential differences between Academic and Administrative and Professional Services staff. In this case, statistically significant differences (95% confidence level) were found in the Task, Intellectual Stimulation and Mentor styles. The first two are present on a higher extent in Administrative and Professional Services staff, whereas the third one on Academic staff.

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Figure 21. Leadership Styles by professional group. Average From 1 (not at all) to 7 (totally).

In the case of the data by professional category, the only statistically significant difference at a 95% confidence level emerged for the Intellectual Stimulation style, between the top management and employees without management responsibilities.

Figure 22. Leadership Styles by professional category. Average From 1 (not at all) to 7 (totally).

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Finally, each participant rated the extent to which they believe their supervisors valued three communal values (“Helping Others”, “Caring for Others”, and “Attending to Others”), power values (“Having power”, “Demonstrating superiority”, and “Having status”), and achievement values (“Being accomplished”, “Being competent”, and “Being successful”) on a scale of “1= Not Important” to “7 = Extremely Important”, following the work by Block et al (2020, *forthcoming*). These scales Cronbach’s alphas show good reliability (0.976, 0.938 and 0.720 respectively).

The following figure shows how women show slightly higher values in two groups of values, being the communal values dimension the only one that presents statistically significant differences.

Figure 23. Perceived Values by sex of the supervisor. Average From 1 (not important) to 7 (extremely important).

No differences are found between Academic and Administrative and Professional Services staff.

Finally, on its side, there is a statistically significant difference (95% confidence level) between employees without specific management responsibilities and top management in the case of Power values, being less present in the people in top management. This difference is illustrated in Figure 24.

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Figure 24. Perceived Values by professional category. Average From 1 (not important) to 7 (extremely important).

4. Concluding Remarks

In general terms, our analysis points to **remaining challenges in our institutions regarding gender equality and the incorporation of stereotypically feminine values** and needs in decision-making. These analyses vary across institutions (see details in the qualitative section) but share general concerns and challenges grouped into different areas.

In terms of values and general dispositions and consistent with previous gender research showing the effects of gender stereotypes in people's identity, women and men identified with similar dispositions in terms of agentic traits (being competitive or courageous), but compared to men, **women rated themselves higher in relation to communal personality traits than men rated themselves** (for women, being sensitive or understanding was more clearly part of their self-definition/identity than for men). This is consistent with gender stereotypes that women are more communal and interpersonally orientated, which translates into an actual greater identification with communal traits and goals. This is important because from a psychological perspective identity traits (the way one defines himself/herself) strongly influences behavior. Interestingly, **employees' tendency to be communal was lower in higher managerial levels (people in top management)**, which is consistent with 'think manager-think male' prototypes about leadership (Koenig et al., 2011; Gartzia & van Knippenberg, 2016), according to which

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leaders tend to adapt to more agentic and stereotypically masculine role definitions as they advance to higher positions. Because organisations need to display increasingly more communion in leadership to be effective (Eagly, Gartzia & Carli, 2012; Gartzia & van Knippenberg, 2016; Gartzia & Baniandres, 2019), these trends suggest that research organisations should more critically consider the referents of leadership traits that they are encouraging for managers.

In a more optimistic tone, results also show that the general perception is that managers in general tend to be more people than task oriented, including top managers, being the mentor leadership style the more perceived by respondents. However, in relation to leadership styles there are also marked differences between women and men leaders. In general and consistent with 'female-advantage' analyses of leadership styles (see Eagly, Gartzia & Carli, 2012 for a review), **women leaders display significantly more interpersonally-oriented leadership behaviors** (i.e., showing more mentoring behaviors and individualized consideration) than men leaders. In contrast, **no differences emerged between women and men leaders in the other (non communal-related) dimensions of leadership:** task-orientation, intellectual stimulation, and contingent rewards.

Also, people are generally satisfied about their work, although **satisfaction levels are generally lower for employees in the Administrative and Professional Services compared to academic staff**, whose satisfaction levels are higher, regardless of gender.

In relation to sexism, there is relative agreement that sexist values still remain a problem in our society, pointing to relatively high levels of awareness about gender equality concerns as a social problem. However, it is important to note that **men, compared to women, considered gender equality concerns less relevant and prevalent in our society.**

The analysis of work-life balance concerns also resulted in remarkable differences between women and men respondents: in all the dimensions studied, **women expressed higher concerns about the biases and obstacles that they encounter in the organisation regarding work-family issues** (they perceived their working environment and managers are generally less supportive of work-life balance than their male colleagues, for whom work-life balance concerns were less marked). In contrast, perceptions of a work-family conflict in one's personal life were similar for all groups, except for people with managerial responsibilities: **top managers experience the highest levels of work-family conflict (but also higher levels of satisfaction with work).**

In relation to perceptions of actions that should be taken to help women advance to managerial positions, the general perceptions show that **women are significantly more in favour of the**

adoption of quotas, believing to a higher extent that this measure can have a positive impact on their work situation.

Together, these results point to **strong effects of gender in variables that are critical for leadership and decision-making in organisations** as well as the satisfaction, work-life balance and general responses of employees, suggesting that gender equality actions should take into account how managerial activities are gendered and influence organisational dynamics at different levels. Among others, **actions should be directed to reducing current gaps and differences between women and men employees and managers so that both women and men and stereotypically feminine styles (i.e., communion and interpersonal orientation) are sufficiently represented in decision-making** within the organisation. These analyses and interventions should take into account the specificities of the different institutions, ensuring that the changes that are designed and implemented to promote gender equality are well aligned with their particular organizational values and strategy, in order to ensure more successful implementation processes of gender equality plans.

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